

Organic field-effect transistors for artificial skin applications using pressure sensor

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Abstract: Recognition of tactile information will be very important for future generations of robots used by humans in daily life for housekeeping and entertainment purposes. An important step to obtain good artificial “electronic skin” is to fabricate large-area pressure sensors with mechanical flexibility. Though, very little progress has been made in the field of pressure recognition compared to the areas of sight and voice recognition. However, flexible materials such as polymers and rubbers have been used to make sensing components. The fabrication of a sensitive skin which consists of thousands of pressure sensors would also require a flexible switching matrix that cannot be realized with present-day silicon-based electronics. Therefore, organic field effect transistors are a good choice for this purpose. They are less expensive for fabrication of a large area and simultaneously suitable for the switching matrix in a pressure sensor. The organic transistors are integrated with a graphite-containing rubber pressure sensor layer to form a very wide area structure providing an ideal solution to realize artificial skin with low-cost processing technology.

Keywords: Electronic skin, organic transistors

Theoretical Actuator Control

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Abstract: Robots typically have an individual actuator at each joint which can result in a non-intuitive and difficult control problem. In this paper, a control method is presented in which the real joint actuator mimics theoretical actuators which can be more intuitive, and hence makes the control problem more straight forward. Our theoretical actuator control method requires a solution to the force distribution problem when applied to parallel mechanisms. An extension of virtual actuators Set Control method is presented. This extended method allows for dealing with if it is not clear how to specify torques at the ankle, knee, and hip joints of a legged robot in order to produce smooth motion of its torso. Control of robots may be made easier if they are equipped with a more intuitive set of actuators and constrained degrees of freedom in which the torque cannot be specified but can be measured, and also describe a method for creating as single theoretical actuator out of several serial chains acting in parallel. This method is useful for controlling multi-legged creatures or multi-manipulator work cells. In future a simulated tripod robot shall be developed to test the proposed control method. The theoretical actuators allowed textbook control solutions to be used in controlling this highly non-linear parallel mechanism. Using a simple linear control law, the robot walks while simultaneously balancing a pendulum and tracking an object.

Keywords: Actuator, Control Mechanics

Vending Machine Controller IC Using Finite State Machine

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Abstract: A vending machine is a machine, which dispenses items such as snacks, beverages, lottery tickets, and consumer products to customers automatically, after the customers insert currency into the machine. Nowadays, Vending Machines are well known in mega cities. The objective of this paper is design a Vending Machine Controller IC. This machine accepts money as an input data and delivers the product to the costumer. The input data (like money) is given to the machine with the help of panel provided on it. Here the facility provided to the user that if he wants his money back in between the process, then he can do it by pushing the button 'CANCEL'. This IC has 22 pins out of which 13 pins are for input and 7 pins are for output and 02 pin has no connection. User can enter currency in five digits by enabling pin 'in' and select one product by enabling that specified (as 'ue', 've', 'we'.. etc.) pin. This quality makes it different from other Vending Machine Controller IC's. The Verilog code for the proposed Vending Machine is developed and simulated in 'ModelSim SE PLUS 6.5'.

Keywords: Vending Machine, ModelSim SE PLUS 6.5

Hybrid Technology for Adaptive Lighting

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Abstract: Now a day's science has solved many problems. But there are still many problems that still remain unsolved, in case, if there exists any solution then that might be somewhat costly to afford. Lighting a dark room or basement in day time is one of them. This paper describes a system by which we can enlighten a dark room with the help of Sun, optical system, optical fibers and paints which has a better reflection coefficient. As the known fact, sun is the permanent source of energy and as well as light. In day time this system will be used to turn light in a dark room or a basement. At first optical mirrors will turn the rays towards the optical fibers and optical fiber will led them to the dark room. The provided dark room is painted by a paint which has good light reflection coefficient. The paint will split the light into the room or basement. This innovative project has only two drawbacks: firstly; it cannot work in rainy days secondly; it is very hard to collect sun rays and sent them to the optical fibers. To solve the second problem we have to make the optical system movable (sun tracker will be used here). This would make the system a bit costly; however the overall system has only one time investment.

Keywords: Optical fibers, reflection coefficient